

SUSTAINABLE AQUACULTURE – BETWEEN THE NEED FOR DEDICATED POLICIES AND RATIONAL RECONCILIATION WITH ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION

Cătălin Eugen PLATON

President of the National Association of Fisheries Producers ROMFISH

Abstract

Although it has a history dating back thousands of years, aquaculture has only come to the attention of society in the last five decades. In Europe, which was the leader in aquaculture production in the 1950 s, after significant development in the 1970s and 1980s, there followed, as in North America, a long period of decline, which continues today. One of the causes of this decline in an agricultural activity that is important for food security was the tightening of environmental restrictions and the lack of development policies. At the global and regional levels, various initiatives to establish a favourable policy framework for the development of this sector have resulted in the FAO Guidelines for Sustainable Aquaculture and, at the European Union level, a recurring set of strategic guidelines. Both are described and analysed from the perspective of producers. On the other hand, the response to unjustified environmental restrictions that do not take into account the specific characteristics of different types of aquaculture can come through a balanced and rational integration into the neoliberal theories of market environmentalism, with all the controversies discussed in this paper. Sustainable aquaculture is a strategic agricultural activity based on economic rationale, carried out in a clear, predictable, and stimulating institutional environment, with a dedicated policy that seeks to satisfy the widest possible range of social interests.

1. Context

It has become a truism to state, at the beginning of any presentation or paper dealing with the subject, that aquaculture is the branch of animal husbandry that has grown the fastest in recent decades. This fact, which is essentially justified by statistical data, is true only for part of global aquaculture, especially in Asia, but it is completely unfounded in the case of aquaculture in the European Union, where stagnation has been evident since 2000, and even less so in the case of Romania, where the sector has shrunk significantly.

Another platitude is the term ‘sustainable aquaculture’, for which there is no legal definition, at least in European legislation, thus joining a more generous list of terms frequently used in current regulatory practice without being legally defined or being defined improperly (e.g. "aquaculture", "extensive", "semi-intensive", "intensive", etc.). In this case, the FAO has developed a framework of principles that promotes economic, social and environmental sustainability in order to meet the growing demand for aquatic food, while respecting the environment and improving livelihoods. At the same time,

although European Union aquaculture has been struggling to survive for a quarter of a century, attempts are also being made in this area to promote "sustainable aquaculture" in a somewhat different approach, focused overwhelmingly on environmental issues, including respect for the biological and "social" needs of farmed organisms. As a counter-reaction to the *wholesale* condemnation of aquaculture, including for its mere existence, by various non-governmental organisations, but also the promotion of these more or less alleged faults in the public sphere by institutional vectors, part of the sector has turned to associating certain types of aquaculture with public environmental services in order to demonstrate its commitment to environmental protection values and increase the sector's relevance in national economies. In the following, we will analyse the visions of the two organisations, how the practical principles can be applied in the European context, and the usefulness of monetising the environmental services generated by responsible aquaculture.

2. **The premises and solutions for sustainable development in aquaculture globally**

The end of World War II, which, as was natural in a post-conflict situation, generated investment enthusiasm for rebuilding economies destroyed by war and consolidating social structures, attracting an increased pace of economic development. Of course, in the background, the dispute between two political systems seeking ever greater hegemony resulted in environmental concerns being ignored, which led to the introduction of an initial mandate for "environmentally sound development" (1972 UN Conference on the Human Environment in Stockholm [1]). Subsequently, in 1978, Ignacy Sachs conceptualised "eco-development" [2], defining it as "an approach to development that aims to harmonise social and economic objectives with ecological management, in a spirit of solidarity with future generations". Consequently, from the outset, the concept was based on three major areas that needed to be harmonised: economic viability, social responsibility and environmental responsibility.

Later, in 1987, the UN report of the World Commission on Environment and Development, entitled **Our Common Future** [3], refined Sachs' concept to the point of abstraction: "*Humanity has the capacity to make development sustainable to ensure that it meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs.*" This succeeded in achieving a consensus at the time, but one that could only be vaguely defined, as Herman Edward Daly, former economist at the World Bank from 1988 to 1994, stated: "*Sustainable development is a term that everyone likes, but no one is sure what it means*"[4]. In practice, the agreed definition included everything, leaving nothing out, but thus becoming sterile.

In 1989, the FAO Council, based on the Brundtland Commission's definition of sustainable development, adopted the definition of sustainable agriculture and rural development as: "*... the management and conservation of the natural resource base, as well as the orientation of technological and institutional change so as to ensure the*

fulfilment and continued satisfaction of human needs for present and future generations. Such sustainable development (in the agriculture, forestry and fisheries sectors) conserves land, water, plant and animal genetic resources, does not degrade the environment, is technically appropriate, economically viable and socially acceptable (FAO 1989) [5]".

This definition applied to the rural economy better described the needs of societies in terms of time and space, but some environmentalists considered it pessimistic, calling for a more positive approach that would improve the environment and biodiversity rather than merely avoiding damage. Furthermore, the definition does not mention the welfare of animals used in agriculture, a concept that has developed in recent decades and which, in some public positions, has now taken the form of eco-extremism [6]. For example, after ten years of litigation, a Polish court sentenced the head of the "Fish" department of a supermarket to one year in prison with a two-year suspended sentence, and two employees of the department to ten months in prison with a two-year suspended sentence. In addition to these sentences, they were also fined for the offence, as fish traders, of *"keeping carp without water and packaging them in plastic bags without water [7]"*.

In 1997, the FAO published Brian Hardaker's work [8], which provides a fairly comprehensive analysis of the implications of applying the concept of "sustainable agriculture and rural development", where, among other things, it marks the evolution of "sustainable development" by achieving a balance between three perspectives: economic, social and environmental protection. In this context, there is also an analysis of the economic-environmental interface, which has generated new ideas on assessing and internalising the (positive/negative) impact on the environment from which the system of monetising environmental services has evolved, which we will analyse in a separate paragraph. The analysis emphasises, in the context of identifying "governance" as a key element in achieving the objective, the role of participation in shaping the policies, strategies or actions of farmers, in their various forms of organisation. Also, in the same context of governance, Hardaker describes the policies that can contribute to achieving balance: direct government action, the use of control and instruments, and the use of economic incentives. Of these three levels of action, Hardeker mentions that economic incentives often offer better solutions to market failures than control measures, suggesting the following incentive approaches: targeted subsidies, tradable resource quotas, transferable individual rights, transferable development rights, tradable emission permits, environmental taxes, resource pricing, effluent taxes, user fees, guarantee-return schemes, environmental bonds.

In the following years, the UN focused [9] on the three pillars considered to be the key elements of sustainability: economic, environmental and social. In addition, in 2015, the UN adopted a universal call to action to end poverty, protect the planet and improve the lives and prospects of everyone, everywhere, through 17, later 22, sustainable development goals that set out the indicators needed to validate the concepts.

As the debate became more specific, it also touched upon aquaculture, where, unlike the European Union, the FAO has always acknowledged and confirmed that aquaculture is an agricultural activity. We will discuss the differences in approach to aquaculture between the EU and the FAO in detail in the following paragraph. Thus, at the 36th session of the FAO Committee on Fisheries in July 2024 [10] , the adoption of the "Guidelines for Sustainable Aquaculture (GSA)" developed and finalised by the twelfth session of the COFI Subcommittee on Aquaculture at its meeting on 16-19 May 2023. They provide a comprehensive framework with technical advice for decision-makers and stakeholders at all levels - international, regional, national and local - on how to expand and intensify aquaculture responsibly. They emphasise the need to balance social, economic and environmental well-being while increasing productivity and profitability in the sector. The GSA are the first international tool dedicated to aquaculture and are aligned with the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development and the FAO Blue Transformation Roadmap. A selection of the main actions that should underpin aquaculture policy, both at national and EU level, is presented below:

- 1. Recognising and prioritising aquaculture, as appropriate, in national food development strategies and plans, and ensuring that aquaculture is integrated into national policies and action plans on food security and nutrition, health and climate ();**
- 2. Developing and implementing policies, strategies and plans, laws and regulations, institutional and administrative arrangements that promote economically efficient, environmentally friendly, technically feasible and socially responsible aquaculture and encourage the active involvement of the private sector and civil society in these processes;**
- 3. Promoting consultation and effective and transparent participation of all stakeholders** and entities involved in or affected by aquaculture in the processes of establishing, reviewing and implementing policy, legal and institutional frameworks, to ensure that their interests are taken into account;
- 4. Providing in national legal frameworks for procedures and mechanisms for reviewing decisions and actions of public institutions** and other stakeholders in aquaculture, as well as for reporting, auditing and enforcement to ensure accountability for decisions and actions;
- 5. Establish and publish guidelines, mechanisms and procedures to clarify the relationship between different stakeholders in the aquaculture sector** and their rights and responsibilities, to guarantee the security and enforceability of property and lease rights, land and water tenure and access rights, and to facilitate access to these for aggrieved stakeholders;
- 6. Ensuring consistency between the policy frameworks for aquaculture and other agricultural sectors**, including fisheries, crop farming, livestock farming, fruit

growing, etc., water management and forestry, in order to provide a predictable and transparent environment for investment in aquaculture;

7. Provide efficient delivery of services and tools essential for the sustainable development of aquaculture, **offering incentives and supporting market-based instruments**;

8. Establishing clear and predictable processes, where appropriate, for authorising or permitting aquaculture activities (e.g. licensing farms), **avoiding unnecessary administrative burdens and costs, overlapping administrative layers at local and national level**, and facilitating communication and interaction between applicants and decision-making authorities;

9. **Strengthen coordination and cooperation between the various authorities responsible** for different aspects relevant to aquaculture development (e.g. sanitary, environmental, health, water, etc.) in order to facilitate the development of relevant legislation applicable to aquaculture, as well as its implementation, and to ensure **simplified administrative procedures**. If possible, a national platform could be created that includes all relevant competent authorities responsible for aquaculture at national and local level;

10. Clear delineation of administrative and decision-making responsibilities, **delegation of decisions to the competent authority**, prior definition and approval of decision-making criteria, timely decision-making and establishment of a mechanism for challenging administrative decisions;

11. Creation of **networks and platforms for dialogue** involving competent public authorities at different levels and other actors, such as aquaculture producer organisations, cooperatives, groups, research, knowledge and innovation institutions, NGOs and CSOs (civil society organisations);

12. Establishing, where possible, **legislation and regulations specific to aquaculture**, while avoiding over-regulation, overlap and conflicts between legislation and regulations, and ensuring that national legal frameworks supporting aquaculture, including aquaculture-specific legislation, are aligned with international legislation and applicable international instruments and standards;

13. Ensuring **the early involvement of the competent authorities in the field of aquaculture in the development of relevant legislation applicable to aquaculture**;

14. Promoting, where appropriate, the use of non-legally binding governance tools, such as a **code of conduct, codes of good aquaculture practice**, and **economic incentives and disincentives**, to complement laws and regulations;

15. Adopt a clear, transparent, fair and inclusive process for **designating suitable areas for aquaculture and sites within each area**;

16. Paying **special attention to the small-scale sector** and supporting the establishment of group farms in suitable areas to enhance technical skills and value chain development through the application of good agricultural practices, continuous on-the-job training, marketing facilities and biosecurity practices;

17. Promoting low-trophic aquaculture species, such as filter feeders, algae/seaweed and bivalve molluscs, which, when properly managed, can provide ecosystem services and reduce the negative impact of other agricultural or non-agricultural activities on surrounding ecosystems;

18. Promoting **aquaculture systems that provide habitat and refuge** for terrestrial and aquatic biodiversity;

19. Developing national policies or strategies for the supply of biological material for restocking, to ensure a constant supply that meets the demand of producers. Such strategies should take into account the role of infrastructure development, such as **the establishment of breeding centres as a source of broodstock** to promote credible seed certification systems;

20. Support **investment in research and innovation** to identify alternative feed ingredients, particularly from local resources, with good nutritional value that optimise feed conversion rates while being environmentally and socially sustainable. These may include insects, algae, single-cell proteins, agricultural by-products and fish/food processing waste;

21. Developing **investment policies and strategies** that attract investors and encourage financial institutions to finance the sector. Strategies should focus on infrastructure, new technologies, capacity building, including training, research and innovation, in order to fully exploit the potential of sustainable aquaculture and support food and nutrition security, poverty eradication, employment, ecosystem protection and restoration, biodiversity conservation, climate change adaptation and mitigation;

22. Establish transparent and verifiable **rules and processes for financing aquaculture** and investments **that enable investors and other stakeholders to be held accountable** in an appropriate business, legal and regulatory environment. These rules and processes should recognise the legal or customary rights of individuals or communities to access land, water and natural resources;

23. **Financial support for investments by aquaculture farmers** who do not normally have access to financing from financial institutions, and through which funds and loans are organised, facilitated and provided to support the implementation of good management practices;

24. **Promoting domestic and foreign investment, financing and insurance schemes** that offer significant potential and opportunities to complement national public resources and enable better access to capital, technology, skills and markets, and help

farmers and other investors along the value chain to reduce risks and expand their activities;

25. Promoting investment in aquaculture research and innovation to improve its economic, environmental and social performance throughout the value chain.

26. Establishing participatory and consultative processes to identify research and development priorities for aquaculture. These should focus on **new technologies and innovations** to unlock the full potential of aquaculture, **while recognising the importance of traditional knowledge, culture and practices**, particularly of communities dependent on aquaculture.

27. Strengthening partnerships by creating and maintaining centres of excellence in aquaculture across industry, academia, governmental and non-governmental actors. This will stimulate relevant and demand-driven research and innovation;

28. Developing information exchange and communication tools accessible to all stakeholders and the general public to combat misinformation and enable informed decision-making;

29. Provide specific capacity-building opportunities, including formal and non-formal education, such as field schools for farmers, women's networks and similar mechanisms to enable women, young people and vulnerable and marginalised groups to benefit equitably;

30. Improve coordination of data collection to support decision-making on the management, monitoring and reporting of sustainable aquaculture and to contribute to policy formulation and implementation.

All of the above elements are the result of an intensive and thorough consultation process and comprehensive scientific analysis, and are in line with the real needs of aquaculture on all continents. They focus on balancing all three fundamental pillars: **economic viability** (investment, support schemes, financing and insurance schemes, economically oriented applied research, supply of affordable aquaculture products), **social responsibility** (the role of aquaculture products in food security, participatory governance, dialogue and information exchange, formal and non-formal education, raising awareness of the specific nature of aquaculture among public bodies and society, communication based on knowledge and transparency) and environmental responsibility (system of incentives and penalties in resource management by identifying, recognising and rewarding environmental services, as well as any quantifiable negative impacts).

The most difficult task in implementing these guidelines is precisely their optional nature, and although both government representatives of FAO member states and representatives of the European Commission (DG Mare) were part of the decision to approve these guidelines for sustainable aquaculture, how they will be translated into concrete actions with measurable results is still uncertain for various reasons, each

taking into account the continental specificity of the various types of aquaculture. On the other hand, these guidelines originate from the Code of Conduct for Responsible Fisheries approved by the 28th session of the FAO in Rome, which took place from 20 to 31 October, with the support and in the presence of delegations from the European Union and its Member States, as well as those that subsequently became members, including Romania. The document [11] states in its preamble: "*The fisheries sector, including aquaculture, provides a vital source of food, employment, recreation, trade and economic well-being for people around the world, both for present and future generations, and should therefore be managed in a responsible manner.*" Although the Code is mainly dedicated to the fishing sector and the protection of natural resources, it also contains a chapter dedicated to aquaculture, which starts from the following premise: "**9.1.1 States should establish, maintain and develop an appropriate legal and administrative framework to facilitate the development of responsible aquaculture.**" Consequently, with a few notable exceptions (Norway, Croatia, Canada, Chile), neither the FAO member states nor the European Union have developed such a legal and administrative framework to govern the sustainable development of aquaculture since 1995. Although, after the Second World War, the US, European countries and Japan made notable progress in the development of aquaculture, subsequently, due to regulatory restrictions, the pace of growth stagnated and they went from being leaders in production [12] to leaders in imports [13] .

The lack of coherence in the European Union's sustainable aquaculture development policies will maintain its contemplative status as a net importer of aquaculture products from other economies. The root causes of this situation and the European Union's approach to sustainable aquaculture will be analysed in the following paragraph.

1. Premises and solutions for sustainable development in EU aquaculture

As far as the European Union is concerned, the current regulations governing aquaculture are confusing, ill-suited and do not fall within the scope of regulations that take into account the specificities of the various forms of aquaculture and respond to modern needs. The fragmentation of competences between Member States and the EU on aquaculture issues is the source of the crisis that has been affecting the sector since the late 1990s. The absence of a coherent legislative approach to the complex issues addressed by aquaculture regulation, such as a Common Aquaculture Policy modelled on the Common Agricultural Policy and based on the same applicable articles of the TFEU, has contributed to the stagnation of this activity and undermined its international competitiveness. As the European Court of Auditors has repeatedly noted, the legislative frameworks and policies adopted by the EU and Member States have been "inadequate", "weak and ineffective", thus contributing to an uncertain future [14] for the aquaculture sector, which is dominated by family businesses, micro-enterprises, small and medium-sized enterprises.

In accordance with the provisions of Article 38(1) and Article 38(4) of the Treaty establishing the European Economic Community (Treaties of Rome, 1957) [15] , a

common agricultural market was established between the signatory states, covering both agricultural production and the marketing of products obtained through this common agricultural policy. In accordance with the provisions of paragraph 3 of the same article, agricultural products were those defined in Annex II to the Treaties. These included, and still include, fish, crustaceans and molluscs.

With the intention of joining the European Economic Community by countries with strong commercial fishing sectors and extensive fishing areas such as the United Kingdom, Denmark (which had total control over Greenland at the time), Norway and Ireland, the issue arose of individualising a common fisheries policy separate from agricultural policy, which was entirely logical, since there are fundamental differences between fishing, as an activity involving the extraction of natural resources from the public domain, and aquaculture, as a zootechnical activity involving the breeding of privately owned fish stocks. In principle, its main purpose was to regulate access to the commercial fishing zones of Member States and to define exclusive economic zones in territorial seas. Aquaculture, which was underdeveloped in the 1950s and 1960s, was taken over, somewhat arbitrarily, by *assimilating* the codes from the Combined Nomenclature (CN) relevant for setting customs duties, thus excluding it from the agricultural policy instruments that were, organically, much more applicable to it.

Thus, while agricultural policy initially aimed to promote domestic production and ensure farmers' incomes comparable to those in other sectors while maintaining product prices that were affordable to consumers, fisheries policy focused on the conservation and management of aquatic resources that were the subject of fishing as part of environmental concerns. The agricultural overproduction crisis of the 1970s led to a series of restructuring of the common agricultural policy, the most important being the MacSharry reform of 1992, which replaced the policy of price protection with a policy focused on compensatory income support linked to a range of eco-conditions. The new form of support was grouped under Pillar I – direct payments. These direct payments subsequently underwent changes and adjustments with Agenda 2000, the 2003 reform of the Common Agricultural Policy and the 2013 reform.

The privileged status of agriculture is based on the fact that, despite the importance of food production, farmers' incomes are around 40% lower than incomes in other sectors. Agriculture is also more dependent on weather and climate conditions than most other sectors, and there is an inevitable time lag between when consumer demand changes and when farmers can respond to that change. It is vital that farmers maintain the profitability of their business, but at the same time work in a sustainable and environmentally friendly way and conserve soils and biodiversity.

For these reasons, the objectives of the Common Agricultural Policy are to:

1. **supporting farmers and improving agricultural productivity, for a stable supply of food at affordable prices;**
2. **protecting farmers in the European Union so that they can earn a decent living;**

3. **contributing to the fight against climate change and the sustainable management of natural resources;**
4. **preserving rural areas and landscapes throughout its territory;**
5. **maintaining the vitality of the rural economy by promoting jobs in the agricultural, agri-food and related sectors.**

To achieve these objectives, the Common Agricultural Policy has developed three key instruments for the agricultural sector:

- **income support through direct payments**, contributing to income stability and rewarding farmers who protect the environment and provide public goods that the market does not generally pay for, such as caring for the countryside;
- **market measures to deal with difficult situations**, such as a sudden drop in demand due to a health alert or a fall in prices due to a temporary oversupply on the market;
- **rural development measures**, with national and regional programmes responding to the needs and challenges facing rural areas.

On the other hand, aquaculture was somewhat arbitrarily captured within the fisheries sector, and the Common Fisheries Policy developed a separate identity, exclusively for the fishing industry, in 1970, through Council Regulation (EEC) No 2141/70 of 20 October 1970 establishing a common structural policy for the fishing industry, which was replaced by Council Regulation (EEC) No 101/76, it covered only commercial fishing. Aquaculture was mentioned for the first time, without any relevant specificity, in Council Regulation (EEC) No 3760/92 of 20 December 1992 establishing a Community system for fisheries and aquaculture, which focused mainly on 'the protection and conservation of available and accessible marine living aquatic resources'.

Beyond the linguistic aspect of the translation of the term 'fisheries', which, in the Oxford Dictionary, means: '1. a part of the sea or a river where fish are caught in large quantities 2. (also fish farm) a place where fish are bred (= kept in order to produce young) as a business', and in Romanian it was translated only as "fishing", it can be seen that aquaculture was discriminated against compared to other agricultural activities, being assimilated with the fishing of public resources, being the only branch of agriculture that never benefited from direct payments.

In the 1990s, the definition of "aquaculture" was similar, in the context of the unification of statistical reporting, both in the FAO's understanding [16] and in that of the Council of the European Union in Regulation (EC) No 788/96 on the provision by Member States of statistics on aquaculture production: "*Aquaculture is the cultivation of aquatic organisms, including fish, molluscs, crustaceans and aquatic plants. Cultivation involves some form of intervention in the growth process to increase production, such as periodic reproduction, feeding and protection from predators. Cultivation also implies individual or associative ownership of the species cultivated or rights derived from contractual agreements. In a statistical sense, aquatic*

organisms that are harvested by an individual or group that has owned them throughout their growth period contribute to aquaculture, while aquatic organisms exploited by the population as a commonly owned resource, with or without appropriate licences, represent the product of fishing.

In 2013, the European Commission reconsidered the definition of aquaculture through Regulation (EU) No 1380/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council on the Common Fisheries Policy, amending Regulations (EC) No 1954/2003 and (EC) No 1224/2009 of the Council and repealing Council Regulations (EC) No 2371/2002 and (EC) No 639/2004 and Council Decision 2004/585/EC, where aquaculture ‘*means the rearing or cultivation of aquatic organisms using techniques designed to increase the production of the organisms in question beyond the natural capacity of the environment, in a system where the organisms remain the property of a natural or legal person throughout the rearing or cultivation stage, up to and including harvesting*’. From our perspective, this definition excludes extensive aquaculture.

Leaving aside these terminological discrepancies, aquaculture has a special status because:

- despite the importance of food production, farmers' incomes are about 50% lower than incomes in other sectors and 10% lower than incomes in other branches of agriculture;
- aquaculture is much more dependent on weather and climate conditions than most other sectors, and especially than other branches of agriculture, because water is the living environment for aquatic organisms and feeding, as in all animal husbandry, depends on cereals and oilseeds;
- there is an inevitable time lag between when consumer demand changes and when aquaculture producers can respond to that change – for example, it takes time to produce more of a particular species. This time lag is longer than in other agricultural sectors because fish have production cycles ranging from 2 to 16 years;
- Aquaculture producers must maintain the profitability of their activities, but at the same time work in a sustainable and environmentally friendly manner and conserve wetlands and biodiversity. Declining profitability and, as a result, the abandonment of the activity not only has economic and social consequences, but also affects the environment by reducing biodiversity, especially in the case of the type of aquaculture practised in Central and Eastern Europe (but also in some countries in the western EU) based on the use of ponds, reservoirs and lakes, which provide 41 environmental services to society, which we will analyse separately;
- Trade uncertainties and the positive impact of aquaculture on the environment justify the important role of the public sector in the lives of farmers.

Although it has a tradition dating back more than two millennia, European aquaculture has focused from the outset on its role in the local or regional economy. Over the last decade of the second millennium, aquaculture production in the EU-28 Member States has grown at a modest pace compared to the growth rates recorded on other

continents. Thus, over the last 30 years, aquaculture in the EU-28 Member States has grown by 28.6%, which is less than 1% per year.

While globally, 2014 marked a turning point in the ratio between global aquaculture and fisheries production, with aquaculture surpassing production from natural stocks through fishing, fisheries production is still predominant in the European Union. Thus, in 2022 [17], the European Union consumed approximately 3.038 million tonnes of fish and other aquatic organisms from aquaculture, of which only 0.835 million tonnes came from domestic production and 2.203 million tonnes from imports, and of the 7.443 million tonnes of fish and other aquatic organisms from commercial fishing consumed, only 0.867 million tonnes came from EU fishing capacity catches. In practice, aquaculture in the European Union provides only 8.0% of the consumption of fish and other aquatic organisms at Member State level, a dramatic decrease compared to 2018.

Structurally, aquaculture is a particularly complex activity, which globally uses over 400 species, being carried out either in fresh water or in marine or brackish environments, using a wide range of fish farming facilities – from earthen ponds, ponds and reservoirs with complex uses, floating installations, tanks made of various materials (concrete, PVC, PE, fibreglass, etc.) – and a variety of farming techniques, from intensive monoculture systems with formulated feed to extensive systems based on the ability of fish species and other aquatic organisms to extract nutrients from natural feed, or integrated multitrophic aquaculture, which uses a combination of species that fully exploit an ecosystem's capacity to generate nutrients and transform the excrement of one species into food sources for other species.

Like any other agricultural activity, aquaculture is carried out exclusively in rural areas, predominantly by micro, small and medium-sized enterprises. At European Union level, according to European Commission data [18], in 2022, there were approximately 13,855 enterprises were active in aquaculture, compared to 15,000 enterprises in 2018, employing around 73,000 people compared to 75,000 employees, i.e. an average of 5 employees per farm.

Compared to the average net income of economic sectors at EU-27 level, which, according to EUROSTAT [19, 20], was EUR 39,058/year in 2022 compared to EUR 34,754/year in 2018, and in aquaculture, according to STECF [21], the average net income of an aquaculture employee was EUR 25,800/year in the same reference period, compared to EUR 25,700/year in 2018, which means an income level 34% lower than in other non-agricultural activities, leading to additional pressure on the workforce, especially for environmentally friendly aquaculture, which is labour-intensive.

Throughout this model of aquaculture development in the European Union, the Commission has adopted strategic guidelines for the development of aquaculture addressed to Member States in 2002 [22], 2009 [23], 2013 [24] and in 2021 [25], but little has changed given their optional nature and the Commission's limited powers in relation to aquaculture, which is mistakenly not considered an agricultural/livestock

activity. In these guidelines, the annual growth target for aquaculture was 4%, while globally the growth of this agricultural sector was 11%. In reality, EU aquaculture has stagnated over the last 25-30 years, with modest growth.

The most recent recommendations, from 2021, are entitled: Strategic guidelines for a more sustainable and competitive aquaculture in the EU for the period 2021-2030. The document identifies, in principle, the same obstacles to the sustainable development of aquaculture, namely achieving a growth rate that is relevant in the context of global competition and ensuring reasonable delivery prices to consumers. This is because, in essence, EU policies related to aquaculture, which are the main obstacles to increasing production, are focused almost exclusively on environmental protection, with the economic component and many of the most relevant aspects of the social component taking a back seat.

Against this backdrop of the EU aquaculture situation in recent decades, in which, despite all the financial efforts allocated to the development of sustainable aquaculture, the EU sector can only cover a very small proportion of market demand and EU producers are unable to produce either in the quantities or at the affordable prices that imports fully provide, the consistent solutions identified to resolve these dilemmas are either to raise production and marketing standards for imported products or to adopt specific policies for EU aquaculture. The first option has the potential to bring the prices of imported products in line with those of EU production. The second option, favoured by producer organisations and the Aquaculture Advisory Council: "The AAC remains firmly convinced of the need to align EU policies on aquaculture, agriculture, animal welfare and fisheries and reiterates its recommendation for a reform of EU aquaculture policy" [26].

Consequently, it is necessary to set binding, quantified targets for increasing sustainable aquaculture production, linked to the various types of aquaculture practised in the European Union, and this requires, first and foremost, a political decision at Union level. Recently, in Communication COM(2025) 75 final from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions [27], the intention to develop a vision for the fisheries and aquaculture sector for 2040 in order to ensure their long-term competitiveness and sustainability to ensure job creation and to address the pressing issues affecting fishing and aquaculture communities. However, over the last 25 years, the EU model of guidelines, recommendations, guides, directives, visions and declarative communications, which do not create legal obligations, continues to be sterile, and the aquaculture sector continues to suffer. For these reasons, EU aquaculture producers insist that the main objective, which can only be achieved through a politically committed Common Aquaculture Policy, must be for the Union of 2040 to be a place where sustainable aquaculture production thrives in all its diversity, where aquaculture is competitive and attractive to future generations, both in terms of employment and investment, ensuring a positive, reasonable surplus in the trade balance of each Member State and the European Union as a whole. Economic development will also stimulate

the social component, both in terms of education, research and innovation, and in terms of public communication, which is at the origin of the concept of 'social acceptability' from which the major premises at the extremes that underpin the environmental protection component at the heart of sustainable aquaculture in the EU derive (). Media campaigns launched by various civil society organisations, based more on perceptions than on scientific data, have only contributed to the stigmatisation of an entire agricultural sector, aquaculture, using simplistic approaches.

2. Ecosystem services generated by sustainable aquaculture

The discretionary exploitation of aquatic resources through commercial fishing initially led to the introduction of restrictions (definition of total allowable catch, establishment of quotas, areas, periods, species prohibited totally or temporarily), justified by the need for sustainable exploitation of natural resources in the public domain in order to maintain the natural capacity of the environment to constantly regenerate its stocks. In addition, there are two other ways of ensuring consumption on the one hand, and the recovery of aquatic organism populations for human consumption and the ecosystem that supports them on the other: ecological reconstruction and aquaculture. The directions that aquaculture has taken in its efforts to keep pace with the ratio between available resources and population growth have not been different from those of other branches of agriculture and have primarily focused on intensification, with the advantage of a considerably larger number of species. However, the intensification of production initially generated a conflict with environmental objectives.

Advocates of biodiversity conservation have reinforced in public discourse the ecocentric view that conservation aims to limit the harmful impact of humans on pristine and wild ecosystems, on valuable habitats untouched by humans and unaffected by human activity, although the distinction between 'natural' and 'anthropogenic' or 'anthropised' ecosystems has become increasingly ambiguous. On the other hand, neo-liberal economic schools have generated the conceptualisation in the utilitarian paradigm of the notion of nature's services, which establishes society's dependence on natural ecosystems and argues for the need for goods and services derived from natural ecosystems, undervalued or completely ignored by society, to be known, evaluated and, ultimately, traded on formal markets in a context that can provide information about their quality or quantity reflected in prices. Although, from an economic point of view, this process of transforming natural services, which require neither capital nor labour and belong to the public domain, into marketable commodities can, following a cost-benefit analysis, justify investment decisions, the elementary dissection ignores the interdependencies and determinations between these elements. Nevertheless, the force displayed internationally by institutions legitimising the new perspective of 'market ecology', namely research and economics, as well as those who generate and promote such solutions through policy instruments, such as

the state, legal systems and academia, has succeeded in imposing the monetisation of environmental services in public discourse and economic practice.

Monetisation associated with market environmentalism has been promoted as a way to reconcile economic growth, resource allocation efficiency and environmental conservation through the application of market-based governance, often mediated by international development agencies, global organisations, private corporations, banks and NGOs. In general, when ecosystem services are transformed into commodities, they become the basis for new socio-economic hierarchies, characterised by the repositioning of existing social actors, the emergence of new ones and, most likely, the reproduction of unequal power relations in terms of access to wealth and environmental resources.

The most refined form of this monetisation is '*payments for ecosystem services*', which economically reward resource managers who, through their activities or responsible management, generate ecosystem services. The "payments for ecosystem services (PES)" system is based on three conditions: (i) there must be an ecological function subject to trade; (ii) there must be a standard unit of exchange; (iii) there must be a legal framework for supply, demand and intermediation flows to be functional.

Between 1995 and 2015, over 550 PSE programmes were active worldwide, with an estimated value of \$42 billion in annual transactions [28], thus demonstrating that the three conditions mentioned above were met and tested. The sources of these payments can be classified as follows: final beneficiaries of services, governments on behalf of third parties, governments through compliance obligations. Consequently, we find that the role of policy instruments in developing the framework for applying these market mechanisms is fundamental. These policy instruments available to decision-makers are: legal and regulatory instruments, instruments based on rights and customary rules, economic and financial instruments, and social and cultural instruments.

Thus, with regard to the relationship between aquaculture and the environmental objectives assumed by the European Union, we can consider as a social instrument the recognition, in *the Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions: A 'farm to fork' strategy for a fair, healthy and environmentally friendly food system*, that aquaculture 'generates a lower carbon footprint than land-based animal production' [29].

Currently, at least in the case of aquaculture, unlike the rest of agriculture, Member States and the EU as a whole are showing clear reluctance to use legal, regulatory and economic-financial instruments, even though various forms of aquaculture undoubtedly qualify as net providers of ecosystem services, being integrated and consolidated into natural mechanisms. The scientific community has acknowledged that, especially in the case of open production systems, i.e. extensive/semi-intensive aquaculture, aquaculture has created wetlands that are among the most productive ecosystems on earth and are of great economic and cultural importance to humankind [30]. The importance that has been attached in recent years to establishing the

ecosystem services that agricultural or fisheries activities provide to society has led to confirmation of the decisive role of aquaculture in the development of these services, particularly traditional carp and associated species aquaculture, which is mainly practised in Central and Eastern Europe. Research carried out in recent years has identified 41 possible ecosystem services [31] (10 provisioning, 20 regulating and maintenance, and 11 cultural) that these anthropogenic aquatic ecosystems can generate. Among the essential contributions that certain types of aquaculture (traditional carp and associated species farming, bivalve mollusc farming or algae farming) make to society are: carbon sequestration, nitrogen and phosphorus fixation, nitrogen and phosphorus extraction in the form of high-quality protein, ensuring hydrological balances in surface and groundwater, ensuring the local microclimate, ensuring social cohesion in rural areas through job creation, creating and maintaining terrestrial and aquatic landscapes, etc.

Although the value of ecosystem services provided by aquaculture in ponds, ponds, multi-purpose reservoirs, lagoons and estuaries, or facilities for farming shellfish or other filter-feeding species is significantly higher than that of any other agricultural sector, support for the complex natural value services created and maintained by aquaculture is virtually non-existent. We emphasise the importance of resolving this contradiction by focusing on the objectives of the EU Green Deal. It is necessary to recognise the value of aquaculture at least on a par with that of agriculture and to establish mechanisms to reward those who, through responsible management, ensure the continuity of these elements that are essential for meeting sustainability criteria, as is the case in agriculture [32].

The lack of financial support for maintaining aquaculture activity in traditional areas has already begun to lead to the abandonment of fish farms, their drying up and their conversion into agricultural land for which they may be eligible for direct payments under Pillar I of the Common Agricultural Policy. From the perspective of the roles that traditional aquaculture plays in terms of ecosystems, habitats and also from a social point of view, this transformation can only have disastrous long-term results and must be stopped through proactive support measures.

In the particular case of fish farming in earthen ponds, an activity with a history stretching back thousands of years [33], considered in Europe as part of the intangible cultural heritage, it is clear that this type of aquaculture, practised in traditional fish farms that are sources of aquatic biodiversity, providing passageways and increased connectivity between freshwater habitats for a variety of taxa that are wholly or partially aquatic, supports greater species richness at the level of the anthropised aquatic ecosystem and greater diversity at the landscape level compared to other freshwater habitats. This is particularly evident in regions where floodplains and wetlands have disappeared due to changes brought about by agriculture and infrastructure development.

However, in-depth scientific studies to inventory, document and evaluate the rewards of responsible management that has maintained these mixed-origin (semi-natural)

wetlands are only just beginning. Recently, the scientific community in Central and Eastern Europe has focused on determining the contribution of fish farming in earthen ponds (basins, lakes, ponds, reservoirs) to the cycles of the main biogenic elements: carbon, phosphorus, nitrogen. Thus, a study conducted in the Czech Republic [34] reaches the following conclusions:

- ▶ Cyprinid farms sequester 34 kg P/ha;
- ▶ The carbon footprint of traditional cypriniculture is 2.9–4.0 kg CO₂ -e kg⁻¹ weight consumed, about five times lower than other agricultural activities, including animal husbandry;
- ▶ The density required to achieve a zero footprint (N and P) is 374.7 kg/ha;
- ▶ The net value of environmental services (provisioning and regulating) of traditional cypriniculture is on average about 2375 €/ha;

Based on studies conducted in Poland [35], the value of non-productive environmental services (excluding provisioning services) is €52,857/ha (of which €881/ha are cultural services, €304/ha are biodiversity maintenance services, with wetland conservation accounting for the largest share);

According to data published in Germany [36], for the state of Brandenburg, the new EMFAF funding guide (European Maritime, Aquaculture and Fisheries Fund 2021–2027) for aquaculture provides for compensation for environmental services for cyprinid farming at €250/ha/year for extensive fish production and measures to maintain ponds and lakes. In the state of Saxony, compensation for environmental services from the same European fund is around €205/ha, but can reach up to €800/ha for actions in ponds of up to 5 ha.

In Hungary, recent studies [37] have identified 16 active ecosystem services and 19 impacts, 15 of which are positive, for traditional cypriniculture. Also in Hungary, in an article [38] on multifunctional fishponds, the amount granted in Hungary's first financial year in the EU for certain environmental services or for the use of sustainable practices was €204/ha/year.

Of course, the above-mentioned values for PES may differ from one country to another depending on the method of assessment, but the differences cannot be very large between countries in Central and Eastern Europe.

3. Conclusions

1. Sustainable aquaculture, although lacking an adequate definition, is based on three essential components: economic viability (without which it cannot exist as an activity), environmental protection (without which it cannot exist), and social acceptability (without which it cannot function).

2. Aquaculture, although lacking a coherent and consistent legal framework, starting with its very definition, has been unjustifiably excluded from the agricultural policy model, being arbitrarily assimilated with commercial fishing.

3. Given the passive response of EU Member States to the recommendations of the European Commission, the European Parliament and the Council on the need to

increase domestic aquaculture production, it is necessary to develop a Common Aquaculture Policy as specified in the TFEU.

4. Although monetising the ecosystem services generated by responsibly managed sustainable aquaculture raises sufficient philosophical, economic and technical controversies, for traditional fish farming it could be an incentive to avoid abandoning fish farms and converting them into agricultural land.

5. Reporting the value of the aquaculture sector in terms of GEP (Gross Ecosystem Product) rather than GDP (Gross Domestic Product), even at a theoretical level, could show the real contribution of aquaculture to national welfare.

6. The involvement of scientific research in analysing international technological and socio-cultural contexts and providing knowledge-based information, both at the level of farmers and at the level of representative bodies or responsible authorities, is fundamental. However, we will discuss the role of research in aquaculture in the next issue.

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